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Effects of Personality on the Performance of Educational Leaders and Teachers at Kasiglahan Village National High School Utilizing the Big Five Personality Test

Sunnylyn B. Ceniza

Abstract: Personality is difficult to assess and evaluate without appropriate, accurate, and proper tools. In support of this, according to the study of Abutalib (2012), psychologists use questions, that report or reflect an individual's feelings, preferences, and behaviors and allocate the individual's responses into numerical values to measure patterns of answers across several items. The study aims to determine the Effects of Personality on the Performance of Educational Leaders and Teachers at Kasiglahan Village National High School utilizing the Big Five Personality Test using t-test, ANOVA, and correlation through SPSS. The study revealed that educational leaders and teachers have the same performance whatever personality type they have and probably personality type might have little to no influence on the performance of educational leaders and teachers. The analyzed data also showed that there is no significant difference in the performance of teachers according to their personality. It can be said that educational leaders and teachers have the same performance regardless of their personality type and the results also signify that the numerical rating of educational leaders and teachers are almost identical which implies that personality has a very low impact on the performance of educational leaders and teachers specifically the personalities categorized Big Five Personality Test. Data revealed that there is a weak negative correlation between the personality of educational leaders and teachers to their performance. Personality can be negatively correlated to the decrease in the performance of educational leaders and teachers. This could mean that by any chance, personality can be a cause of the decrease in the performance of educational leaders and teachers, but the weak negative correlation possibly occurred by chance in the sample and there is not enough evidence to state that this correlation exists in the teaching personnel of Kasiglahan Village National High School.

Keywords: Personality, Educational Leaders, Teachers, Educational Management, Big Five Personality Test

1.1 Introduction

The idea of using personality traits as a tool to predict job performance dates back to the early 1900s. Scholars at that time saw no link between personality and job performance (Abutalib, 2012). Guion and Gottier (1965) thought that personality tests were a weak way of predicting job performance and selecting employees. Their findings went unchallenged for another 25 years. There were several reasons why nobody made the connection between personality and job performance: personality traits were not clearly defined; thousands of personality traits existed conceptually, which made it difficult to distinguish between them; some traits had the same name, which led to contradictory personality measures results and outcomes, studies conducted in that period were narrative rather than quantitative. Sarcasically, many commented on the period before 1990s the time when individuals didn't have personalities. (Guion and Gottier, 1965, Abutalib, 2012)

Personality is difficult to assess and evaluate without appropriate, accurate, and proper tools. In support to this, according to the study of Abutalib (2012), psychologists use questions, that report or reflect an individual's feelings, preferences, and behaviors and allocate the individual's responses into numerical values to measure patterns of answers across several items. This approach is believed to provide useful insight into an individual's behavior in the workplace (Anderson, M.G., 2007 & Abutalib, 2012).

That is why understanding your personality and the personalities of others is critical. This is because personality and other individual differences are relatively stable over the life course. Personality matters because it is linked to social behavior in organizations. Personality may affect our work habits and how we interact with our coworkers (Scandura, 2016. P.86)

The duties and responsibilities of each occupation require people in those roles to behave in specific ways for successful performance. Because personality helps determine preferences, temperaments, and behavior, personality influences job performance by determining whether an individual has a natural inclination for job duties and/or will enjoy the job. Certainly, other personal characteristics (e.g., cognitive ability, education, experience) also influence job performance, but personality plays an important role. (Anderson, 2007)

In this sense, the idea of the personality-performance relationship can now be measured using instruments provided by professionals and experts, through various and thorough research and assessment. It shows how one's personality might affect his/her performance at work. Over the years, leaders tend to accept the fact that the personality type of employees can influence their decision on how to deal with them and how they interact with their colleagues or others at the workplace based on different research and studies.

One advantage of using personality to predict how well a person would fit a role is that it displays no bias against particular groups, classes, ages, ethnicities, or genders; concerning itself only with the behavior of the subject. (Abutalib, 2012). For this matter, in predicting job performance, personality traits or types of the employee must always be considered and assessed properly. Therefore, personality traits is one of the behaviors that differentiates one person from another (Beer & Brooks, 2011, Abutalib, 2012). And according to the study of Abutalib (2012), it also provides insight into the specific job for the person. It will determine why some people have the same level of education, knowledge, and skills but some can do better jobs than others (Sackett et.al. 2002, Abutalib, 2012). If the personality traits are suited perfectly to the jobs they are doing, they are seen to be stable and steady throughout their

work life (Denissen et.al., 2011; Gerber et.al., 2011, Abutalib, 2012).

People in the organization possess different personalities that a leader needs to understand and assess. Designating the right person for the right job is vital for a leader to be able to achieve the organization's mission, vision, goals, and objectives. Putting the right person for the right job empowers the employee and helps them to become effective and efficient employees in the organization. Doing the job that fits their personality type can boost their performance to different levels. It is indeed that the personality types of a person can influence and affect his/her performance. In this way, the leader can empower their employee to do the things that they love and fit their personality type. According to Scandura, individual differences are aspects of OB that must be understood, and leaders must often work with them rather than try to change people. (Scandura, 2012. P.86)

Job prediction based on personality helps to determine whether a person would enjoy their occupation (Tett and Burnett, 2003, Abutalib, 2012) and reminds us that "people enjoy being themselves", which is good for their well-being and motivation, in turn, leads to high performance in the workplace (Anderson, M. G., 2007 and Abutalib, 2012). That is why Barrick, M. R., and Mount, M. K. (1991) echo this point, saying that workers become effective when they occupy a position that matches their personality traits. (Abutalib, 2012)

Therefore, personality assessment can help ensure success by identifying the right individual for each work environment. (Anderson, 2007). In this sense, for better and successful performance, personality of people in the organization must properly assess and determine.

Understanding personality of people in the organization can contribute to the success of an organization in achieving objective into particular project, program or activity. Their personality type somehow determines their effectiveness and efficiency in a particular job once their personality considered and valued.

Nowadays, with our more sophisticated understanding of personality traits, a belief prevails that personality assessments can positively contribute to performance at work. Nevertheless, Barrick and Mount still see questions to be answered, and warn that understanding the nature of personality traits and attempting to predict their links with work performance is a complex affair (Barrick, M. R. and Mount, M. K., 2005, Abutalib, 2012).

Understanding the personality of people within the organization is vital, able for everyone to be functional and effective employee. Because according to Scandura, at the workplace, everyone has something to offer, and it takes all types of people for teams and organizations to be effective. For a leader, this underscores the importance of understanding individual differences because to build effective teams, everyone needs to feel valued to be engaged. (Scandura, 2012. P. 88).

This study aims to determine the Effects of Personality on the Performance of Educational Leaders and Teachers at Kasiglahan Village National High School utilizing the Big Five Personality Test.

2.1 Review of Related Literature and Studies

Personality

Personality is a set of emotional and behavioral characteristic that surround and assist a person in his daily life. (Albert,

2006 Qasemia et. al, 2015). Personality traits are one of the behaviors that differentiate one person from another (Beer & Brooks, 2011, Abutalib, 2012, Salaudin, et al, 2019) and provide acumen whether a person will do some specific job, in comparison to others (Sackett et al, 2002).

Personality matters because it is linked to social behavior in organizations. Personality may affect our work habits and how we interact with our coworkers (Scandura, 2016. P.86). People behave within the organization based on the personality type that they possess. Their personality determines how they will behave at the workplace and influences how they interact to people within the organization and affects their performance at work.

Brody and Ehrlichman pointed out personality is, “those thoughts, feelings, desires, intentions, and action tendencies that contribute to important aspects of individuality.” (N. Brody and H. Ehrlichman, 1998, Anderson, 2007) Personality is a combination of internal, and intangible characteristics and therefore cannot be measured directly. Instead, psychologists rely on self-reports of a person’s thoughts, feelings, preferences, and/or behaviors to assess personality—that is, they ask people questions about themselves, assign numerical values to their responses, and use these values to generate a portrait of the person taking the assessment. (Anderson, 2007).

In this research, the Big Five personality test by Costra and Mc Crae (1992) was used to identify and determine the personality type of the teacher-respondents. The five-factor model of personality as measured by the NEO-personality Inventory-Revised (NEO-PI-R) includes Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness. (Mc Crae and Costa, 1997). According to Qasemia et. al, (2015), the Big Five model also has been considered the highly accepted and widely known personality model for the last almost two decades. Hogan and Shelton (2006) pointed out that personality theories examine the variances and similarities in a person. The similarities can be used to predict one’s performance and behavior, as they provide the collective attributes of human nature. (Hogan and Shelton, 2006, Qasemia et al, 2015). Experts in the field of personality are of the view that individuals have long-term traits that affect behaviors at work. (Gerber et al, 2011 Qasemia et al, 2015). Concerning research on personality, some scholars captured that personality is an effective tool that predicts job performance. (Ozar & Benet-Martinez, 2006; Schulman, 2011, Qasemia, et al, 2015). Other studies indicated that there is a strong connection between the big five personality dimensions with an ability to communicate and reliance. (Martis, 2007 and Qasemia, et al 2015).

Organization composed of different people with different personality. People behave within the organization according to personality traits or type that they have. Scandura pointed out that, at the workplace, everyone has something to offer, and it takes all types of people for teams and organizations to be effective. For a leader, this underscores the importance of understanding individual differences because to build effective teams, everyone needs to feel valued to be engaged. (Scandura, 2012. P. 88)

Performance

Job performance is a multi-dimensional construct which indicates how well employees perform their tasks, the initiative they take and the resourcefulness they show in solving problems. Furthermore, it indicates the extent to which they complete tasks, the way they utilise their available resources and the time and energy they spend on their tasks (Boshoff & Arnolds, 1995; Schepers, 1994, Rothmann and Coetzer, 2003 and Klang, 2012).

McCloy, Campbell, and Cudeck (1994) and Viswesvaran and Ones (2000) indicated that job performance refers to how resourcefully individuals take action and contribute with behaviors that are in line with an organization's objectives. (McCloy et al, 1994, Viswesvaran and Ones, 2000 and Klang, 2012).

In this study, performance is based on the result of the IPCRF of the respondents. The correlation of personality and performance will help school administrators and key leaders to understand and realize the possible effect of personality on the performance of educational leaders and teachers.

Job performance could be affected by situational factors, such as the characteristics of the job, the organization, and co-workers (Hackman & Oldham, 1980; Strümpfer, Danana, Gouws & Viviers, 1998 and Rothmann and Coetzer, 2003), and by dispositional factors. Dispositional variables can be described as personality characteristics, needs, attitudes, preferences, and motives that result in a tendency to react to situations in a predetermined (predisposed) manner (House, Shane & Herrold, 1996, Rothmann and Coetzer, 2003). Job performance is influenced by aptitude, need for achievement, self-regard, locus of control, affective temperament, and the interaction between these constructs (Boshoff & Arnolds, 1995, Wright, Kacmar, McMahan & DeLeeuw, 1995, Rothmann and Coetzer, 2003). In this sense, personality can influence or affect the performance of people within the organization. With this, the researcher seeks to determine and identify the correlation between personality and performance.

According to Goldberg (1993), evidence has suggested that personality measures are valid predictors of diverse job-related criteria (Goldberg, 1993 and Rothmann and Coetzer, 2003) and can enhance fairness in personnel decisions (Rothmann and Coetzer, 2003). Recent research showed that personality dimensions are related to job performance (Rosse, Stecher, Miller & Levin, 1998; Wright et al., 1995 Rothmann and Coetzer, 2003).

In this research, the relationship between personality and job performance of teachers and educational leaders at Kasiglahan Village National High School was analyzed through the Big Five Personality Test.

2.2 Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the Effects of Personality on the Performance of Educational Leaders and Teachers at Kasiglahan Village National High School utilizing the Big Five Personality Test.

Specifically, this study seeks to find answers to the following queries:

- What is the performance of educational leaders and teachers based on their personality types?
- Is there any significant difference between the performance of the teachers based on their personality types?
- Is there any significant statistical correlation between the personality types of educational leaders and teachers to their performance?

2.3 Hypotheses

- There is no significant difference in the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction according to their education, position, and designation.
- There is no significant correlation between the perception of educational leaders and teachers on job satisfaction and their performance.

3.1 Methodology

Research Design

This descriptive research aims to assess the personality types of educational leaders and teachers in Kasiglahan Village National High School through the utilization of an adapted instrument, and the gathered data and results can be a basis for the formulation of programs, projects, and/or activities to address possible issues towards understanding educator's personality and its possible effect to their performance as a member of the organization. This involves statistical treatment such as ANOVA and correlation on the mean score on the score of educational leaders and teachers on the personality type test and the performance using the IPCRF of educational leaders and teachers.

Participants

The participants of the study are educational leaders and teachers of Kasiglahan Village National High School on a voluntary and non-compulsory basis. There are 90 volunteer educational leaders and teachers who represent all eight (8) academic departments. Teachers will self-assess their personality type through the adapted instrument with a 5-point Likert scale (1-Disagree to 5-Agree).

Instrument

To achieve the objective of this study, the researcher adapted and revised the survey instrument from the works of the NEO Big 5 Scales. The questionnaire is composed of 25 items that can be considered as indicators to determine your personality type within the Big Five Personality Test. To determine the personality type of educational leaders and teachers, items will be rated on Five (5) a point Likert scale and were scored as 5-Agree, 4-Slightly Agree, 3-Neutral, 2-Slightly Disagree, and 1-Disagree.

The total score per set of indicators will determine the personality type of educational leaders and teachers then it will be analyzed through ANOVA as well as if the personality of educational leaders and teachers is correlated to their performance based on the IPCRF of the respondents.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research tool/instrument was administered on volunteer teachers. The data gathered out of the Likert questionnaire will be analyzed through statistical treatment such as, ANOVA, and correlation utilizing the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Data Analysis Tool

The data analysis tool will be mean, ANOVA, and correlation with the use of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Table 1
Performance of Educational Leaders and Teachers Based on Their Personality

Personality	Performance	
	Numerical Value	Verbal Interpretation
1 Agreeableness	4.024	Very Satisfactory
2 Openness	3.894	Very Satisfactory
3 Conscientiousness	4.047	Very Satisfactory
4 Neuroticism	3.812	Very Satisfactory
5 Extraversion	4.071	Very Satisfactory

Table 2
Significant Difference Between the Performance of the Teachers Based on Their Personality

Descriptives

Performance

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
					Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Agreeableness	41	4.0245	.25259	.03945	3.9448	4.1042	3.00	4.37
Openness	23	3.8938	.35047	.07308	3.7422	4.0453	3.00	4.85
Conscientiousness	17	4.0473	.27787	.06739	3.9044	4.1902	3.49	4.47
Neuroticism	2	3.8120	.26587	.18800	1.4232	6.2008	3.62	4.00
Extraversion	7	4.0711	.08581	.03243	3.9918	4.1505	3.99	4.22
Total	90	3.9943	.28105	.02962	3.9354	4.0532	3.00	4.85

ANOVA

Performance

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.425	4	.106	1.368	.252
Within Groups	6.605	85	.078		
Total	7.030	89			

Table 3
Significant Correlation Between the Personality Types of Educational Leaders and Teachers to Their Performance Correlations

		Personality	Performance
Personality	Pearson Correlation	1	-.190
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.073
	N	90	90
Performance	Pearson Correlation	-.190	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.073	
	N	90	90

Table 3 shows that there is a weak negative correlation between the personality of educational leaders and teachers to their performance. Personality can be negatively correlated to the decrease in the performance of educational leaders and teachers. This could mean that by any chance, personality can be a cause of the decrease in the performance of educational leaders and teachers.

The r-value of .073 is greater than the level of significance of .05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. There is no significant statistical correlation between the personality types of educational leaders and teachers to their performance. The weak negative correlation possibly occurred by chance on the sample and there is not enough evidence to state that this correlation exists in the teaching personnel of Kasiglahan Village National High School.

4.1 Conclusion

Personality can be negatively correlated to the decrease in the performance of educational leaders and teachers. This could mean that by any chance, personality can be a cause of the decrease in the performance of educational leaders and teachers but the weak negative correlation possibly occurred by chance in the sample and there is not enough evidence to state that this correlation exists in the teaching personnel of Kasiglahan Village National High School.

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Instrument

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